

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL

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Annotation. In the article, the role of education in the development of human resources in our country was analyzed in its duration, quality and role of education in human life, during its activities, importance, research on this topic. Conclusions and proposals have been cited to provide a wider range of education in Human Resource Development.

Keywords: Education, Human Resources, Human Capital, Development, Innovation, Economy, life expectancy, lifestyle.

Introduction

A person and his abilities, knowledge, and skills have become the main factor of the well-being of any society and the economic development of the state. Today, human capital, without a doubt, appears as a priority direction of social economic policy in Uzbekistan. Because the development of human capital is a necessary condition for the development of innovative economy, knowledge economy, investments, global information systems, the latest technologies and new forms of business. Among the various characteristics that make up human potential, human capital represents the characteristics that affect the change of income, in this respect, human capital includes the knowledge, practical application and skills of the worker accumulated on the basis of special education, vocational training and production experience.

Today, in the developed countries of the world, in particular, the USA, Great Britain, Canada, France, Germany, Japan, South Korea, the main reason for the development of the country is the investment aimed at strengthening the human factor, that is, the development of human potential, the increase in the level of education of the population and professional training of personnel.

The way to ensure the priority economic growth of countries is found in the field of human resources development at the modern stage, precisely in the field of improving the quality of education. It is also worth noting that today the trend of development of education in developed and developing countries of the world is changing. Based on the Asian model of education, the educational process is focused on the development of the skills of practical application of knowledge gained from theoretical knowledge, and the formation of independent learning skills in students based on information technologies.

Literature review.

Human capital is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities used to meet the various needs of a person and society as a whole. The term was first used by the American

economist Jacob Mincer in 1958, then Theodore Schultz in 1961 and Gary Becker from 1964 developed these ideas to form an economic approach to human behavior based on the effectiveness of investments in human capital. For example, according to G. Becker, — human capital is a collection of innate abilities and acquired knowledge, skills and motivations, which (at the level of an individual of an enterprise or society) can be used to increase income. [3]. Human capital is formed by each specific person and it is inseparable from the personality of a living person. It is clear that at first, human capital meant only the sum of investments that are specific to a person's work ability - education and professional skills. By the present time, attention to the concept of human capital has increased and serious emphasis is being placed on the development of this concept.

Genkin (2000) recognizes the development of human resources as an indicator that determines the quality of labor productivity, which is manifested as a source of income. The author includes health care, education, professional skills and mobility as such qualities.

Methodology

After the 60s of the 20th century, almost all definitions of human capital followed a comprehensive interpretation principle:

- *human capital is not only a sum of knowledge, but also human skills, qualifications and abilities;*
- *gradual transformation of human opportunities and potentials into capital;*
- *promotion of health, educational level, motivation and investment do not fundamentally change the socio-economic content of human capital.*

Currently, the countries of the world are implementing a systematic comprehensive reform phase related to the transition to an innovative and digital economy. Due to fundamental changes in the external world, existing paradigms no longer meet modern requirements. In this case, it is related to the knowledge and conquest of nature from the leadership of natural and technical sciences, man, society, their rationality sciences about the balance of nature and society based on evolution took over the leadership.

Education as the most important factor of human development, economic, political, a great influence on the solution of the whole complex of social and humanitarian problems proved to show. These include:

- *living standards for the current period in each country ensuring the level and quality of life;*
- *ensuring effective employment;*
- *reducing the level of social inequality;*
- *strengthening the structure of civil society;*
- *observance of human rights and their effective implementation;*
- *creation of conditions for the full and comprehensive realization of a person's potential.*

The international community appreciates the importance of education in today's world to ensure the appropriate role of education in human development developed a series of strategic programs aimed at

implementing them is taking measures. One of them is the concept of "Education for all". The main principles of the concept were stated in 1990 at the conference organized in Jomtien (Thailand). At this conference, the universal declaration "Education is for all" was adopted. Human rights are universal in this document declaration and the Convention on the Rights of the Child the following was announced: "Every child, young and old person has his own educational needs, in the highest and most perfect sense of this concept, has the right to satisfactory education". Implementation of the policy of reforming and renewing the society for education in Uzbekistan special attention is paid as a crucial part of the increase. Education sustainable development of the country's economy, the country to the world community is considered a mandatory condition for integration.

Analysis and discussion of results.

China's experience of the Asian countries in terms of attention to the quality of education is noteworthy. Only 15-17 percent of the adult population in China is illiterate. If we compare this indicator with other Asian countries, India has -47%; in Bangladesh-61%; -59% in Pakistan; -27% in Iran; -17% in Turkey; In Indonesia it is -15% (Oripova, 2014).

Figure 1. The number of labor resources in our country

Based on the data of Figure 1, it can be said that the number of labor resources in our country continues to increase year by year. The result of this can be explained by the improvement of the standard of living of the population in Uzbekistan. At the same time, the increase in labor resources will also cause employment problems in the future. It forms the need to develop state programs in order to help the population to find employment, and, of course, as a result, it creates the need to develop human resources based on the requirements of the time. The need for these professions decreases and causes

unemployment

(Fig.

2).

Figure 2. The number of unemployed people in our country

Figure 2 shows that in relation to labor resources, the unemployment rate in 2022 is 6.8%, compared to 2020, the rate is 8.1%, i.e. 1.3%. we can see that it is reduced to . So, the results of employment of the population in our country are giving positive results. Human resources are also developing in terms of skills and knowledge, as a result, the level of employment is also increasing.

In developed countries, investments in human capital are seen as an important factor for increasing competitiveness and ensuring economic growth at the micro and macro level. Improving the quality of human capital, consistently implementing the strategy aimed at improving people's professional skills and experience on the basis of continuous education throughout their life is an important condition for ensuring the sustainable development of the economy. The processes taking place in the world economy clearly show that the ratio is changing among the factors affecting the socio-economic development of the country. During the study of the composition of global national wealth by the World Bank on the example of 141 countries of the world, it was known that the share of human capital in its total value is 64%, and its volume has increased by 55% over the last 20 years. In high-income countries that are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the share of human capital in national wealth was 70%, while in low-income countries, its share was 41%. It should be noted that today the factors of economic growth are changing. Instead of traditional factors (labor, land, capital, entrepreneurial ability), science and education, that is, in general, the intelligence of the nation, are coming to the fore. In Uzbekistan, the share of human capital in the structure of national wealth is 62%, according to the experts of the World Bank, the share of physical capital in the structure of national wealth in countries of the world is on average 16%, and natural capital is 20%. , human capital is -64% (in developed countries such as Germany, Japan, Sweden, the share of human capital in national wealth reaches 80%).

The world-famous statesman, the first Prime Minister of Singapore, Lee Kuan Yew, stated in "The Miracle of Singapore" that "we invest in the right policies and human capital." That is, 1 dollar invested in human capital will return 100 times after 10 years and 1000 times after 20 years.

It can be seen from today's demand and foreign experience that the development of intellectual culture is of urgent importance. Modern science and professions can only be mastered by having and sharing one's own opinion as an individual. In the development of many developed countries, especially Japan, Malaysia, Singapore and South Korea, the education system has become crucial. Today's development Japanese are putting before us the issue of personnel training in the fields that are in great demand in the labor market of these countries. At the present time, such professions and trades have appeared in the world market that most of them are prepared in a very short time, not in three or one year, but in ordinary educational centers. There are many examples of this.

Conclusion

The development of man and society is a single process. Production intensive development, development of science and technology, culture and art a better life of a person, the maturation of his spiritual world is for The key to these processes is the education system and the education given to a person quality and size. Therefore, states and societies should strive to create opportunities for education for everyone.

It activates the improvement of the efficiency of the use of human resources and contributes to development. Despite the complex structure of human resources, the specific features of its formation and development determine the importance of the educational components of the development process during the evolution of the scientific concept. It is knowledge and skills that form the basis of human resource development, increase the competitiveness of its carrier in the labor market and determine the level of earning.

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